

THE RELATION BETWEEN WORKPLACE FRIENDSHIP AND SCHOOL CULTURE PERCEPTION OF TEACHERSⁱ

Yasemin Neslihan Bilgin¹ⁱⁱ

Bilgen Kiral²

¹Teacher, Ministry of National Education,
Umurlu High School,
Aydin, Turkey

²Asst. Prof. Dr., Aydin Adnan Menderes University,
Faculty of Education,
Aydin, Turkey

Abstract:

In this study, it was aimed to determine the relationship between high school teachers' workplace friendship and school culture perceptions. The research was carried out with a total of 330 teachers from 8 Anatolian high schools and 8 vocational high schools selected by stratified sampling method in Efeler District of Aydin Province, Turkey in the 2017-2018 academic year. When the data were analyzed, 8 data collection tools which were filled in and which did not carry normality conditions were removed without investigation and analyzed through 322 data collection tools. In the collection of the data "*Personal Information Form*" created by researchers; "*Workplace Friendship Scale*" that it developed by Nielsen, Jex and Adams (2000), adapted to Turkish by Kiral (2016) and the "*School Culture Scale*" developed by Terzi (2005) was used. An exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis was conducted for the construct validity of the School Culture Scale. In the analysis of the data, t-test, Kruskal Wallis H-test, ANOVA, Scheffe test were used. The Pearson Moments Multiplication Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the relationship between workplace friendship and school culture perception of high school teachers. According to the results of the research, it was found that the "*friendship opportunity*" and "*task culture*" perceptions of the high school teachers were higher than the other dimensions. The friendship prevalence of female teachers is higher than that of male teachers; the friendship prevalence and general friendship of married teachers is higher than that of single teachers; the bureaucratic culture perception level of high school teachers in the age group of 35 and under is higher than 41-45 age group; the achievement culture

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ⁱⁱ Correspondence: email yaseminnbilgin@gmail.com

perception level of vocational high school teachers is higher than that of Anatolian high school teachers. Positive and significant relationship between workplace friendship and school culture was found.

Keywords: culture, organization culture, school culture, workplace friendship

1. Introduction

Societies are consisting of organizations arised from people. No matter what kind of organization; communication, interaction, thoughts and ideas of the people within the organization caused the friendship of the workplace. Because most of human beings pass in more than half of their lives in business environment. This period is so long that inevitably leads to friendship at the workplace. "*Workplace friendship*" is defined as the friendship created through shared thoughts and feelings at work. Workplace friendship is important for individuals and organizations because workplace friendship provides emotional support to the individual, getting better work performance, helping to create a good career development and working atmosphere. According to Hays (1988), friendship is a voluntary relationship between two people, which includes sincerity, love and solidarity in order to meet social and emotional needs. However, Wright (1985) describes friendship as an action based on the desire to establish a mutual and equal relationship.

Individuals tend to make friends because they have social needs. Despite this tendency, there are a number of factors that affect friendship at work. Some of these factors are personal such as gender, emotional status (Sias, Heath, Perry, Silva & Fix, 2004) and others factors happen inside and outside of the workplace (Mao, Chen & Hsieh, 2012). Because of these factors, workplace friendship is an important parameter for leadership and management. Also, many researches have shown that individuals who had good workplace friendships can be more productive than others. Boyd and Taylor (1998) concluded that the employees made work easier and faster because of their friendship to the leader and each other. Furthermore, the pressure and stress of the workplace on the employees can be reduced depending on workplace friendship (Lin, 2010). It should not be overlooked that workplace friendship has benefits as well as abuses. Because workplace friendship can cause gossip, sexual harassment, short-term loyalty neutrality, and political organization (Okoe, Boateng & Mensah, 2016).

Nielsen, Jex and Adams (2000) attempted to measure two dimensions of workplace friendship; friendship opportunity and friendship prevalence. Song (2005) changed these dimensions and defined two other dimensions: friendship perception as the existence of the opportunity of improving the relationship of the employees with the superiors in the workplace and friendship quality as the quality of relationship between upper and subordinates. In the study, workplace friendship dimensions of Nielsen, Jex and Adams (2000) were used and these dimensions are explained below:

The Perception of Friendship Opportunity Dimension: Friendship opportunities have been developed to examine the extent to which employees talk to each other and

establish informal relationships with other employees at work (Hackman & Lawler, 1971). This perception includes behaviors such as finding opportunities to know friends at workplace, working collaboratively with friends, and communicating easily with friends everywhere. For this dimension, it is important whether workplace friendship is supported by the workplace (Nielsen, Jex & Adams, 2000; Yavuzkurt, 2017).

The Perception of Friendship Prevalence Dimension: In this dimension, it is aimed to determine the presence of friendship in the workplace. This perception includes behaviors such as talking about personal issues with friends in the workplace, sharing secrets, discussing work-related issues, and whether or not friendship only remains in the work environment (Nielsen, Jex & Adams, 2000; Yavuzkurt, 2017). It is important for organizations to analyze workplace friendship well. Thus, organizations serve the development of social structure. Organizations in which people make friendships find inside the society. Just as societies have cultures, organizations have their own cultures. Organizational culture can be considered as the heart of businesses. Therefore, it is the most important building stone of the enterprises. The culture of organization contains the traditions of the individuals and the environment where the organization is located. In addition, culture constitutes organization-related activities that an organization should undertake and the value judgments of the organization that affect the ideas and behaviours of the organization. The most important of these values are the commitment and responsibility of the individuals within the organization (Ouchi, 1989). The more shared values the members of an organization have, the higher the organizational culture. The high degree of culture increases the organizational commitment and reduces the degree of quitting of their jobs of organizational members (Robins & Judge, 2015). One of the first studies to describe organization culture is the study of Peters and Waterman (1989). In their study, organization culture were examined into the seven dimensions: the way of managing uncertainty, the level of being in favor of movement, the level of proximity to the customers, the level of entrepreneurship, management mentality, the simplicity of the organizational structure and the control of organization (Peters & Waterman 1989). The organizational culture dimensions used in this research are explained as follows (Terzi, 2005):

Support Culture: Employees in this culture participate in decisions taken by the management. A high level of harmony, sharing and mutual support among employees within the organization is the dominant concept. Mutual commitment to the organization is high and there is confidence among employees. There are more informal relationships within the organization than formal relationships. Auditing is performed informally (Ipek, 1999).

Success Culture: In this culture, successful accomplishment of works by individuals is more important than obeying the rules. There is a flexible bureaucracy in the organization; employees solve their own problems. Management does not intervene in decisions taken at lower levels (Terzi, 2005).

Bureaucratic Culture (Role Culture): There is a hierarchical structure in this culture. The organization is pyramid structure. The activities of the employees are determined

by the rules and job descriptions. The mechanization of the individuals and excess of paperwork are often seen in bureaucratic culture (Terzi, 2005).

Task Culture: It is a work-oriented organization and organizational goals are important than individual goals in this culture. The source of power and influence depends on expertise. There are many project groups within the organization (Ira & Sahin, 2011). By looking at the characteristics of these dimensions which give important information about the culture of the organizations, it can be determined what kind of culture the organization has and the efficiency of the work can be increased in the study of the learned culture. It can also provide information on how to get ideas about disruptive aspects of organization.

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this research is to determine the perception of the workplace friendship and school culture of the high school teachers working in Efeler District of Aydin Province, Turkey in the 2017-2018 academic year. In response to this general objective, the following questions were sought:

1. How are the perception levels of high school teachers' workplace friendship and school cultures on the basis of dimension and in general?
2. Do the perception levels of high school teachers' workplace friendship and school culture vary by demographic variables?
3. Is there any meaningful relationship between perception levels of high school teachers' workplace friendship and school culture?

2. Material and Methods

In this section research design, population and sample size, data collection instruments and data analysis are given.

2.1. Research Design

Relational screening model was used to determine the relationship between workplace friendship of high school teachers and organizational culture perceptions (Balci, 2009; Karasar, 2012).

2.2. Population and Sample size

The universe of the research is composed of 1156 teachers working in 22 official high schools in Efeler District of Aydin Province, Turkey. Frequencies of participants for gender, age, marriage status, educational status, term of employment and the organization where s/he works were given in Table 1.

Table 1: Frequencies of participants

Variable		Frequency	%
Gender	Male	148	46
	Female	174	54
Age	35 years old and below	33	10.2
	Between 36 and 40 years old	48	14.9
	Between 41 and 45 years old	92	28.6
	Between 46 and 50 years old	84	26.1
	51 years old and over	65	20.2
Marriage status	Single	35	10.9
	Married	287	89.1
Educational status (graduate from)	Vocational school of a university	15	4.7
	Faculty	268	83.2
	Graduate school	39	12.1
Duration of employment in that high school	Between 1 and 5 years	114	35.4
	Between 6 and 10 years	134	41.6
	Between 11 and 15 years	33	10.2
	16 years and more	41	12.7
The organization where s/he works	Anadolu High School	137	42.5
	Vocational High Schools	185	57.5

In Table 1 as could be seen, the sample was divided into two groups as Anatolian high school and vocational high school with stratified sampling method. Three hundred thirty teachers working in 16 high schools (8 of them are the Anatolian high school and 8 of them are vocational high schools) were selected by simple random sampling method.

2.3 Data Collection instruments

The Workplace Friendship Scale and School Culture Scale were used to collect the research data. The characteristics of these two scales used in the research are explained below.

Workplace Friendship Scale: It was developed by Nielsen, Jex and Adams (2000) to determine workplace friendship. This scale was adapted to Turkish language by Kiral (2016) and he carried out the validity and reliability studies. The adapted scale consists of 10 items and it was 2 dimensional and 5-point likert- type scale. Likert scales provide a range of responses to the given propositions and there are 5 categories of response; strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Undecided (3), Agree (4), Strongly Agree (5). In this study, the sub-dimensions of the workplace friendship scale are the Dimension of Perception of Friendship Opportunity, and the Perception of Friendship Prevalence. Each one consists of five items. As a result of the confirmatory factor analysis for these ten items, two-factor structure fit indices were determined ($\chi^2 = 73.57$, $SD = .34$, $SRMR = .042$, $CFI = .98$, $NFI = .97$, $NNFI = .98$ and $GFI = .95$, $RMSEA = .066$). These data show that the two-factor structure of the workplace friendship scale provides structural validity. The Cronbach Alpha values for this survey were found to be .82 for friendship opportunity, .76 for friendship prevalence and .85 for general friendship. According to Tavsancil (2014), Cronbach's Alpha values of .60 or higher are quite reliable and .80 or

over indicates that the scale is highly reliable. The scale is quite trustworthy in the dimension of "friendship prevalence" and is highly trustworthy in the dimension of "friendship opportunity" and "general friendship".

School Culture Scale: "The School Culture Scale" was developed by Terzi (2005). Short form of this scale, a twelve-item school culture scale, was used to determine the school culture in this study and The Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) coefficient was found to be .764. This KMO value is higher than the recommended minimum value of 0.50 for factor analysis (Tavsancil, 2014). The chi-square values obtained as a result of Bartlett test were found to be significant ($\chi^2 = 938.629$, $df=66$, $p=0.000$)

These results show that there is sufficient correlation between the items in order to perform factor analysis on the sample. Basic components analysis and varimax vertical rotation were performed to determine the structural validity of the scale (Tavsancil, 2014). As a result of the factor analysis, a 4-factor structure explaining 62% of the total variance was obtained. As a result of Varimax transformation, 9 items with factor load values below .10 were subtracted from the scale. After removal of these 9 items, other 8 items with a factor load value of less than .40 were taken out of the scale and the scale was finalized. Factor loadings are the basic criterion for evaluating the results of factor analysis. The factor loadings of the items in the scale range from .576 to .864. Accordingly, the load values of the bureaucratic culture, support culture, success culture and task culture factors are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Factor Loads

Factors	Item	Factor load	Alpha internal consistency coefficient
Bureaucratic Culture	Rigorous measures are taken against violation of the rule.	.864	.73
	There is strict control over the prevention of irregularities.	.815	
	There is an authoritarian sense of administration.	.727	
Support Culture	Personal feelings and thoughts are shared.	.744	.68
	People love each other.	.728	
	People are valued.	.668	
Success Culture	Successful teachers and students are rewarded.	.802	.63
	Everyone gets paid for doing their job well.	.704	
	The biggest prize is to achieve a job.	.625	
Task Culture	Everyone works for the academic success of their students.	.773	.60
	Enough effort is made to achieve the goals of the school.	.619	
	It is essential to work to be "better" than other schools.	.576	

In Table 2 as could be seen, the factor load value should be greater than .33 in order for the item to measure a certain structure (Buyukozturk, 2005). The alpha internal

consistency coefficient calculated for the scores obtained from whole scale is .73. As a result of the confirmatory factor analysis, the fit indices of the 12-item, four-factor structure was determined (χ^2 (50) = 119.26, df = .50, SRMR = .05, CFI = .93, NFI = .97, NNFI = .91 and GFI = .95, RMSEA = .066). When the ratio of χ^2 and the degree of freedom (df) is lower than 3, it indicates a perfect fit between data and the original model (Sumer, 2000; Kline, 2005). In this study, the school culture scale was evaluated according to χ^2 / df ratio which was 2.39 and this result suggested to the perfect fit.

Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) examines the covariance differences between the universe and the sample. If the RMSEA value theoretically closes to zero, this suggests that there are no differences between the sample and the universe covariances. When the RMSEA value is smaller than .05, it indicates a perfect fit. However, the values between 0.05 and 0.08 indicate the good fit (Joreskog & Sorbom, 1993). Thus, calculated RMSEA value is .066 in this study, which indicates a good fit.

Furthermore, due to the large sample size ($n=322$), other values obtained from confirmatory factor analysis were also calculated. The NNFI, CFI, GFI, AGFI and standardized RMR values were calculated as .91, .93, .095, .92 and .05, respectively. The Non-normed Fit Index (NNFI) is developed against the disadvantage of Normed Fit Index regarding being affected by sample size. The comparative fit index (CFI) gives information about the discrepancy between the data and the hypothesized model. The goodness of fit index (GFI) and adjusted goodness of fit index (AGFI) values inform about the extent of the model which measures the covariance matrix in the samples. Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (standardized RMR) notifies the square root of the discrepancy between the sample covariance and the model covariance matrix. The Non-normed Fit Index (NNFI), comparative fit index (CFI), goodness of fit index (GFI) and adjusted goodness of fit index (AGFI) values over .95 are indicating a perfect fit while the values between .90 and .95 indicate the good fit (Hooper, Caughlan & Mullen, 2008; Sumer, 2000). RMR and standardized RMR values are between .05 and .08 indicating good fit (Brown, 2006). The results of confirmatory factor analysis prove that there is a good fit between the items.

2.4. Data Analysis

SPSS 18 (Statistical Package Program for Social Sciences) and Lisrel 9.30 Student programs were used to analyze the data of this study. Parametric, nonparametric and Pearson Momentler Correlation tests were used for analysing data. Frequency, percentage and mean were the parameter used to define the data. The demographic characteristics of the high school teachers who participated in the research were determined using the Personal Information Form. Prior to the analysis of the data, it was checked whether the data provided the normality conditions. By subtracting eight data set that do not meet normality requirement, statistical processes were performed on 322 data set. Statistical analysis of the sample showed that the measures of central tendency were close to each other. The kurtosis (a measure of the peakedness of a distribution) and skewness (a measure of the asymmetry of the distribution of a

variable) confident were determined between -1.96 and +1.96 within the normal limits (Can, 2017).

The level of perception of workplace friendship and school culture of high school teachers was determined by using mean and standard deviation. Student's t-test and ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) test were used according to the independent variables (sex, age, marital status, educational status, study period at school, school type). However, non-parametric Kruskal Wallis H test was used for cases where normality conditions were not suitable. When the differences were formed among the ANOVA test results, the Scheffe test was used as a post-hoc test. The relationship between the variables of the study was tested by a correlation analysis. The correlational relationships among the scales were assessed as small (.10-.29), medium (.30-.49) and large (.50-1) (Cohen 1988). Also, the score of five-point Likert scale was determined as strongly disagree (Very Low: 1.00-1.80), disagree (Low: 1.81-2.60), neutral (Moderate: 2.61-3.40), agree (High: 3.41-4.20) and strongly agree (Very High: 4.21-5.00). Furthermore, the findings were evaluated at the 5% significance level in the 95% confidence interval.

3. Findings

In this section, perceptions of teachers' workplace friendship and organizational culture are examined on the basis of dimensions and demographic variables and given below in tables.

3.1. Descriptive Statistics of Perceptions of Teachers' Workplace Friendship on the Basis of Dimensions

It was determined the descriptive statistics of perceptions of teachers' workplace friendship. The mean and standard deviations of the scores obtained from the data analysis were calculated. These descriptive statistics on the basis of dimensions were given in Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of the Workplace Friendship Dimensions

Dimensions	$\bar{x}$	SD	Ranking
Friendship Opportunity	4.08	.607	1
Friendship Prevalence	3.80	.650	2

It could be seen in Table 3, the mean of perception of the "Friendship Opportunity" was 4.08; "Friendship Prevalence" was 3.80; the mean of perception of the general friendship was calculated as 3.94. The descriptive statistics on the perception of the high school teachers' workplace friendship (n=322) were given in Table 4.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on the Perception of Workplace Friendship

Item	Description of items	$\bar{x}$	SD	Ranking
6	I have formed strong friendships at my school.	4.27	.666	1
1	I have the opportunity to get to know my coworkers in my school.	4.21	.789	2
2	I can cooperatively solve the problems, that I've encountered at school, with my coworkers in my school.	4.15	.736	3
5	In my school, informal talks are tolerated by the management as long as the work is completed.	4.07	.728	4
10	In my school, I do not feel that anyone I work with is my real friend (Reverse coded item).	4.06	.951	5
4	In my school, communication among employees is encouraged.	3.99	.822	6
3	I have the chance to visit the my coworkers at their home.	3.98	.884	7
7	I socialize with my coworkers outside the school.	3.93	.900	8
9	One of the reasons I'm looking forward to being in my school is to see my coworkers	3.59	.922	9
8	I share my secrets with my friends at school.	3.13	1.08	10

3.2. Significance of the Perceptions of Teachers' Workplace Friendship According to Demographic Variables

The student's t-test was applied to examine the perceptions of teachers' workplace friendship according to both gender variable and marital status variable. The sample used was consisted of 148 male and 174 female high school teachers where 35 of them were single and other were married. The results were given in Table 5.

Table 5: Analysis of the Perception of Teachers' Workplace Friendship According to Gender and Marital Status Variables

Dimension	Gender	$\bar{x}$	SD	t	p	Marital status	$\bar{x}$	SD	t	p
Friendship Opportunity	Male	4.06	.612	.373	.710	Married	4.11	.605	1.86	.063
	Female	4.09	.604			Single	3.90	.594		
Friendship Prevalence	Male	3.71	.658	2.46	.014*	Married	3.83	.639	2.57	.011*
	Female	3.88	.633			Single	3.54	.687		
General Friendship	Male	3.88	.568	1.61	.108	Married	3.97	.556	2.49	.013*
	Female	3.98	.555			Single	3.72	.575		

As seen in Table 5, the perceptions of high school teachers about friendship opportunity and general friendship do not show a significant difference according to gender. However, perceptions of high school teachers regarding the friendship prevalence dimension show a statistically significant difference according to gender. Female teachers' perception of workplace friendship ($\bar{x} = 3.88$) is higher than male teachers ($\bar{x} = 3.71$). Effect size is low, $\eta^2 = .02$ (Buyukozturk, 2005). Therefore, it can be said that about 2% of the variance observed in friendship prevalence scores is due to gender. Also, perceived levels of high school teachers in friendship opportunity do not show significant difference according to marital status. However, the perception level of friendship prevalence and general friendship are statistically significantly different according to marital status. Perception of married high school teachers' workplace friendship is higher than that of single teachers ($\bar{x} = 3.54$) in the dimension of friendship prevalence ($\bar{x} = 3.83$). The effect size ($\eta^2 = .02$) is moderate (Buyukozturk, 2005).

Therefore, it can be said that about 2% of the variance observed in friendship prevalence dimension scores depends on the marital status variable. Cohen d value is .46. The difference between the mean scores of friendship prevalence dimensions of married and single teachers is .46 standard deviation.

3.3. Descriptive Statistics of Teachers' Perceived Dimensions of School Culture Perceptions

According to school culture scale, the task culture dimension has the highest mean ($\bar{x} = 4.00$). It is followed by the support culture dimension ($\bar{x} = 3.85$), achievement culture dimension ($\bar{x} = 3.65$) and bureaucratic culture dimension ($\bar{x} = 2.78$), respectively. The mean of total culture perception were determined as 3.57. The descriptive statistics on school culture perception are given in Table 6.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics on School Culture Perception

Item	Description of items	$\bar{x}$	SD	Ranking
4	Enough effort is made to achieve the goals of the school.	4.11	.648	1
22	The biggest prize is to achieve a job.	4.06	.775	2
2	It is essential to work to be "better" than other schools.	3.99	.843	3
18	People are valued.	3.97	.667	4
6	Everyone works for the academic success of their students.	3.92	.834	5
7	People love each other.	3.85	.714	6
24	Personal feelings and thoughts are shared.	3.74	.778	7
21	Successful teachers and students are rewarded.	3.49	.967	8
25	Everybody gets provision to do their job well.	3.40	.899	9
15	There is strict control over the prevention of irregularities.	3.01	.980	10
13	Rigorous measures are taken against violation of the rule.	2.76	.945	11
19	There is an authoritarian sense of administration.	2.58	1.01	12

As seen Table 6 according to school culture scale, the task culture dimension has the highest mean ($\bar{x} = 4.00$). It is followed by the support culture dimension ($\bar{x} = 3.85$), achievement culture dimension ($\bar{x} = 3.65$) and bureaucratic culture dimension ($\bar{x} = 2.78$), respectively.

3.4. Significance of Teachers' School Culture Perceptions by Demographic Variables

ANOVA test and Scheffe test were used to examine teachers' school culture perceptions according to age in Table 7.

Table 7: Analysis of school culture perception according to age variable

Dimension	Age group	n	$\bar{x}$	SD	df	F	p	Signif. Difference
Support Culture	35 years and under	33	3.91	.516	4; 317	.941	.440	
	36-40 years	48	3.86	.599				
	41-45 years	92	3.76	.597				
	46-50 years	84	3.90	.513				
	51 years and over	65	3.89	.563				
Achievement Culture	35 years and under	33	3.61	.761	4; 317	1.13	.341	
	36-40 years	48	3.62	.663				

	41-45 years	92	3.56	.699		
	46-50 years	84	3.77	.646		
	51 years and over	65	3.66	.618		
	35 years and under	33	4.01	.609		
	36-40 years	48	3.92	.551		
Task Culture	41-45 years	92	3.94	.594	1.06	.374
	46-50 years	84	4.07	.588		
	51 years and over	65	4.08	.559		
	35 years and under	33	3.16	.850		
	36-40 years	48	2.78	.779		
Bureaucratic Culture	41-45 years	92	2.63	.754	2.83	.03*
	46-50 years	84	2.81	.797		1-3
	51 years and over	65	2.76	.756		
	35 years and under	33	3.67	.504		
	36-40 years	48	3.55	.471	2.34	.055
Total Culture	41-45 years	92	3.47	.420		
	46-50 years	84	3.64	.392		
	51 years and over	65	3.60	.368		

As shown in Table 7, one-factor analysis of variance among the groups was conducted to examine the effect of age variation on school culture. High school teachers were divided into five groups according to their age as seen in Table 7 (Group 1: 35 years and under, Group 2: 36-40 years, Group 3: 41-45 years, Group 4: 46-50 years, Group 5: 51 years and over). According to the school culture scale scores, there was only a statistically significant difference in the bureaucratic culture dimension at $p < .05$ level between Group 1 and Group 3 according to age variable: $F_{(4,317)} = 2.83$, $p < .05$. Despite reaching statistical significance, it appears that the real difference between the average scores of the groups is quite small. The effect size calculated using Eta square was found to be .03. Post-hoc comparisons using Scheffe test indicate that the mean score for Group 1 ($\bar{\chi} = 3.16$, $SD = .850$) is significantly different from the mean score for Group 3 ($\bar{\chi} = 2.63$, $SD = .754$).

In order to examine the teachers' perceptions of school culture according to the marital status variable, t-Test, a statistical method, was applied. The results obtained from t-Test evaluation are given in Table 8.

Table 8: Analysis of School Culture Perception According to School Type Variable

Dimension/ Variable	School Type	n	$\bar{x}$	SD	df	t	p
Support Culture	Anatolian H. School	137	3.79	.594	320	1.661	.098
	Vocational H. School	185	3.90	.533			
Achievement Culture	Anatolian H. School	137	3.51	.668		3.138	.002*
	Vocational H. School	185	3.75	.658			
Bureaucratic Culture	Anatolian H. School	137	2.71	.653		1.405	.161
	Vocational H. School	185	2.83	.874			
Task Culture	Anatolian H. School	137	4.03	.623		.555	.579
	Vocational H. School	185	3.99	.549			
Total Culture	Anatolian H. School	137	3.51	.437		2.222	.027*
	Vocational H. School	185	3.62	.410			

According to Table 8, it is observed that the mean scores of 322 high school teachers' scores on the school culture scale did not show any significant difference according to the support culture ($t_{(320)} = 1.661$; $p > .05$), task culture ($t_{(320)} = .555$; $p > .05$) and bureaucratic culture ($t_{(320)} = 1.405$; $p > .05$) dimensions compared to the school type variable. However, there is a meaningful difference between high school teachers' Success Culture ($t_{(320)} = 3.138$; $p < .05$) dimension and Total Culture ($t_{(320)} = 2.222$; $p < .05$) dimension of school culture. Anatolian High School teachers are lower than perceived levels of achievement culture dimension ($\bar{x} = 3.51$) and vocational high school teachers ($\bar{x} = 3.75$). The obtained Eta square statistic ($\eta^2 = .03$) indicates a small effect size (Buyukozturk, 2005). According to this, it can be said that about 3% of the variance observed in points of success culture depends on the school type. The calculated Cohen d value is .56. The difference between the mean scores of Anatolian High School and vocational high school teachers in achievement culture dimension is .56 standard deviation. When we look at the total cultural dimension of the table, the average scores of the vocational school teachers' scores on the school culture scale ($\bar{x} = 3.62$) are higher than the scores of the school culture scale average scores of the Anatolian high school teachers ($\bar{x} = 3.51$). The obtained Eta square statistic ($\eta^2 = .02$) shows a small effect size (Buyukozturk, 2005). According to this, it can be said that about 2% of the variance observed in the points taken on the total culture dimension depends on the school type. The calculated Cohen d value is .40. The difference between the average scores of Anatolian High School and vocational high school teachers in the total cultural dimension is up to 40 standard deviations.

3.5. Relations between Teachers' Perception of Workplace Friendship and School Culture

Correlation test between high school teachers' workplace friendship perceptions and school culture perceptions was conducted. Findings obtained as a result of this test are given in Table 9.

Table 9: Relative Findings between Workplace Friendship and School Culture Perceptions

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Friendship Opportunity	1							
2. Friendship Prevalence	.61**	1						
3. General Friendship	.89**	.90**	1					
4. Support Culture	.52**	.42**	.52**	1				
5. Achievement Culture	.33**	.22**	.48**	.48**	1			
6. Bureaucratic Culture	-.07	-.02	-.05	-.01	.03	1		
7. Task Culture	.52**	.33**	.47**	.54**	.47**	.29	1	
8. Total Culture	.45**	.33**	.43**	.70**	.73**	.50**	.73**	1

p value is significant at the level of .01 ** and .05 *.

It could be seen in Table 9, the relationship between high school teachers' workplace friendship and school culture perception level was investigated by using the Pearson moment product correlation coefficient. The assumptions of normality, linearity and covariance were checked by preliminary analysis. The results of the analyzes made are

given in Table 9. According to this, the perception of friendship opportunity of high school teachers is high level, positive and meaningful correlation with friendship prevalence ($r = .61$; $p < .01$), general friendship ($r = .89$; $p < .01$), support culture ($r = .52$; $p < .01$), task culture ($r = .52$; $p < .01$); the perception of friendship opportunity of high school teachers is positive, meaningful and moderate level correlation with achievement culture ($r = .33$; $p < .01$) and total culture ($r = .45$; $p < .01$). The perception of friendship prevalence of high school teachers is high level, positive and meaningful correlation with general friendship ($r = .90$; $p < .01$) and is positive, meaningful and moderate level correlation with support culture ($r = .42$; $p < .01$), task culture ($r = .33$; $p < .01$), total culture ($r = .33$; $p < .01$). However, there is a positive, low level and significant correlation between achievement culture ($r = .22$; $p < .01$). The perception of general friendship of high school teachers is high level, positive and meaningful correlation with support culture ($r = .52$; $p < .01$) and is positive, meaningful and moderate level correlation with achievement culture ($r = .30$; $p < .01$), task culture ($r = .47$; $p < .01$), total culture ($r = .43$; $p < .01$). The perception of support culture of high school teachers is high level, positive and meaningful correlation with task culture ($r = .54$; $p < .01$), total culture ($r = .70$; $p < .01$) and is positive, meaningful and moderate level correlation with achievement culture ($r = .48$; $p < .01$). The perception of achievement culture of high school teachers is high level, positive and meaningful correlation with total culture ($r = .73$; $p < .01$) and is positive, meaningful and moderate level correlation with task culture ($r = .47$; $p < .01$). It is seen that the perception of the task culture of the high school teachers has a high positive correlation with the total culture ($r = .73$; $p < .01$).

4. Results and Discussion

When looked at the descriptive statistics of high school teachers' workplace friendship, teachers say, *"I have formed strong friendships at my school."* The average expression has the highest average. The item that has got the lowest mean is *"In my school, I open my secrets to friends."* From these two items, it can be said that the teachers are willing to make friends with each other at work, but they do not trust their friendships enough.

Ong (2013) stated in his research that workplace friendship was positively correlated with trust in colleagues. He also stated that workplace friendship plays a critical role in shaping the confidence that employees have in their colleagues, and that this will affect their work behavior. When looking at the sub-dimensions of the workplace friendship scale, *"In my school, I have the opportunity to get to know my coworkers."* in the dimension of *"friendship opportunity"* is ranked first in the highest average. The item that has got the lowest mean is *"In my school, I have the chance to visit and talk to the coworkers whenever I want."* The item that is *"In my school, I have the opportunity to get to know my coworkers."* was found to have the highest mean in Yavuzkurt's (2017) study.

Nielsen et al. (2000) found the same item as the highest mean item in their work. On the findings of the *"Friendship Prevalence"* dimension, *"I have formed strong friendships at my school."* while in the highest order with the highest average, *"In my school; I open*

my secrets to friends." the item is at the bottom of the list. This is because of the political policies that exist in the country. These political policies may have reduced confidence in people. When the descriptive statistics between dimensions are taken into account, it is seen that the highest dimension is the *"Friendship Opportunity"*. It is seen that the average of *"General Friendship Dimension"* is higher than the value range of the five-point Likert scale. This may be due to the fact that employees in the line of affairs and tasks develop positive attitudes in support of employees by the managers at the school or workplace and by the policies at work. Workplace friends being affected by their parents can be involved more duties.

According to the demographic variables, the sense of workplace friendship of the high school teachers shows a meaningful difference in the *"Friendship Prevalence"* according to the gender variable. Yavuzkurt (2017) found that there was a meaningful difference only in the dimension of friendship opportunity compared to the gender variable in the study, and emphasized that the level of perception of friendship among women are higher than that of men. Song (2006) found that men had a higher sense of workplace friendship than women in their work on government employees. That's for two reasons. The first is that 72% of the employees of the government are male and 28% are female. The second reason is that the level of employment of female employees is low.

In this study, female employees are more than male employees but the difference between them is not very high. The fact that women are more sensitive than men in friendship may be the result of this. In addition, the similarities between the problems faced by female teachers may have helped them establish friendships. It is supported by research conducted by Veniegas and Peplau (1997) and Sapadin (1988). High school teachers' sense of workplace friendship is significantly different according to the marital status variable, *"Friendship Prevalence Dimension"* and *"General Friendship Dimension"*. Married teachers have a higher average than single teachers in the dimension of friendship prevalence. One of the reasons for this is that the vast majority of teachers are married. In addition, the problems shared by married teachers may be similar, so that the proliferation of shared things can bring teachers closer together. Mao (2006) also found that married employees have higher perceptions of workplace friendship. The perception of workplace friendship of high school teachers in both dimensions and general dimension does not show a significant difference in age, education, the study period in the school, and the school type variable.

When looked at the descriptive statistics about the school culture of high school teachers, *"Enough effort is made to achieve the goals of the school."* has the highest average. The item with the lowest average is *"There is an authoritarian sense of administration."*. Given these two items, teachers' school culture perceptions are aimed at realizing school goals. They also state that the school administration approach is not authoritative. When we look at the sub-dimensions of the school culture scale, *"Support Culture"* dimension *"People are valued."* while the item is ranked first in the highest average, the item *"Personal feelings and thoughts are shared."* is at the lowest level with the lowest average. From the findings of the research, it can be said that there is a more

humanistic culture in high school. It can be assumed that the administrators have created a culture that values people. But it can be said that the teachers do not share their feelings and thoughts with each other enough when performing them.

On the findings of the high school teachers' dimension of "*Achievement culture*", "*The biggest prize is to achieve a job.*" while the item is ranked first in the highest average, the item "*Everybody gets provision to do their job well.*" is at the bottom of the list. In the high school, it can be said that in the achievement dimension of the school culture is success-oriented. It can be considered that high school teachers prefer to achieve a work much than the prize. The fact that the education system is test-oriented may also be the result of this conclusion. When we look at the dimension of the school culture scale in terms of "*Bureaucratic Culture*", "*Rigorous measures are taken against violation of the rule.*" has the highest rank in the highest averages, whereas the item "*There is an authoritarian sense of administration.*" has the lowest average.

According to these results, it can be said that the teachers working in the high school think that they are under martial law by school administration. But it can also be stated that there is no perception of an authoritarian administration mentality. When we look at the average scores of the "*Task Culture Dimension*" scores of the high school teachers, the item of "*Enough effort is made to achieve the goals of the school.*" has the highest average. The item of "*Everyone works for the academic success of their students.*" is the lowest average item. Given these results, it can be said that the school culture perceptions of high school teachers are focused on success. It may be considered that high school teachers have worked hard enough to achieve this success. When the descriptive statistics between dimensions are taken into account, it is seen that the highest dimension is the "*Task Culture*" dimension. This is followed by "*Support Culture*", "*Achievement Culture*", "*Total Culture*" and "*Bureaucratic Culture*" respectively. It is seen that the average of the total culture dimension is higher than the value interval of the five-point Likert scale. According to these findings, it can be said that the high school teachers are performing their duties in the first place and on time. In doing so, it can be said that they are supported by colleagues and management, and all of them are in the expectation of success as a result. Furthermore, according to school culture perceptions, it is believed that high school teachers see their schools bureaucratically at the lowest level.

According to demographic variables, school culture perception, gender, marital status, educational status, and the study period in the school did not show any significant difference. The school culture perception of high school teachers shows a meaningful difference in the "*Bureaucratic Culture Dimension*" according to the age variable. This difference is between teachers aged 31 and under and teachers aged 41-45. Bureaucratic culture perceptions of teachers 31 and under years old are higher. The reason for this may be that teachers who are new to their job and who have less tenure are success-oriented and stick to the rules when doing their jobs. As the age progresses, the increase of experience may be the reason to change the thoughts of 41-45 age.

A significant difference was found between school type and school culture perceptions of high school teachers. In the culture of success and total culture, it has

been found that the teachers in the vocational high schools have higher school culture perceptions than the teachers in Anatolia. Paker (2014), Ozturk (2015), Alkan (2008) and Sahin (2017) found results supporting the current work. This may be due to the fact that the number of teachers working in vocational high schools is high and that there is a tendency to focus more innovation and change on larger schools.

When looked at the friendship opportunity of the workplace friendship scale, it is found that there is a positive and meaningful relationship with the friendship prevalence, general friendship, support and task culture at a high level. It has got a positive, moderate level, and meaningful relationship with achievement culture and total culture. When we look at the friendship prevalence dimension, there is a positive, high level and meaningful relationship with general friendship. It has a positive, moderate level and meaningful relationship with support culture, task culture, total culture. It has a positive, low level and meaningful relationship with success culture.

When looked at support culture, there is a positive, moderate level and meaningful relationship with success and task culture. It has a positive, high level and meaningful relationship with total culture. There is a high level, positive and meaningful relationship between the achievement culture and total culture. It has a moderate level, positive and meaningful relationship with task culture. There is a moderate, positive meaningful relationship between bureaucratic culture and total culture. There is a high level, positive and significant relationship between task culture and total culture. According to the findings, it can be said that as the friendship opportunity increases, friendship prevalence, general friendship, support and task cultures increase. As friendship relationships between teachers increase, their trust increases and they support each other in any problem experienced. Thus, it can be said that they exhibit higher positive attitudes towards work and tasks.

Dotan (2007) argues that when there are reliable friends in the workplace employees will feel committed to their work, satisfied and comfortable. This statement supports the current work. Gunlu, Donmez, Minal and Omuris (2010) indicate that the performance of employees increases with their supervisors and friendship level. They also stated that because of the friendship relationship in their work, employees will accept extra work, be willing to take on new responsibilities related to work, perform better than expected, and reach their supervisor more easily. All of this can be said to lead to an increase in employees' perceptions of support and task culture. Salem and El-Said (2014) have found that the sense of friendship opportunity has high and positive and meaningful relation with the friendship prevalence and general friendship. In the study of Caliskan (2011), emphasis on sharing information among the employees of the organization and supporting informal communication channels are important to increase the psychological strengthening perceptions of the employees, and expressed more freedom, choice, decision making and self-sufficiency perceptions about the work of the employees. This is also possible with friendship in the workplace. Because workplace friendship increases communication and information sharing among employees.

In Kanbur's (2015) study, it was found that the employees had a high level of positive and meaningful relationship between the general workplace friendship perception and the friendship opportunity perception and the friendship prevalence perception. Bicer and Buyukyilmaz (2016) have found results in support of the current work in their work. As stated by Song (2006), workplace friendship motivates employees to better serve organizational goals, higher organizational productivity and business participation. Lin (2010) notes that workplace friendships play a critical role in shaping the confidence that employees have in their colleagues, and that this can affect business behavior.

According to Kosar and Yalcinkaya (2013), as the level of confidence of the teachers in the institutions and the colleagues, they work with increases, the citizenship behavior increases. Also, as the level of confidence of the teachers increases, the perceptions of organizational culture also increase. Thus, it can be said that teachers can exhibit behavior to exchange opinions with other teachers, to cooperate, to protect each other's rights, to help them to share their workloads. According to the findings of the research, it can be said that there is a low, negative, non-significant relationship between teachers' perception of workplace friendship and bureaucratic culture. Mao, Chen and Hsieh (2009) studied the relationship between bureaucracy and workplace friendship. They found that there was a low, negative, meaningful relationship between them. They pointed out that organizations with bureaucratic organization attitudes negatively affect their workplace friendship. They say that organizations with a high perception of bureaucratic culture will cause a decrease in friendship of workplace. This supports the current work. All these studies and findings show that when the sense of workplace friendship between teachers is supported, organizational culture perception is increasing, and an increase in teachers' organizational identity, focus on task, job satisfaction, and job attachment can be observed.

5. Recommendations

School administrators can support workplace friendship formation by organizing picnics, social meetings and sport activities after work. School administrators can create environments for both in the school and out of the school for male teachers to come together. School administrators can increase the sense of workplace friendship of single teachers by organizing social events that bring together single teachers with married teachers. The relationship between school types of leadership and workplace friendship can be examined in order to help managers to create school cultures.

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